

Data management plan for project "Smart injectable nanoparticle-loaded hydrogel for synergic and targeted treatment of osteomyelitis (SinGel)"

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is prepared in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research project "Smart injectable nanoparticle-loaded hydrogel for synergic and targeted treatment of osteomyelitis (SinGel)" (Nr. LZP-2025/1-0108), 01.01.2026-31.12.2028. The project is implemented in the Faculty of Pharmacy at Rīga Stradiņš University and Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis. The DMP contains descriptions of datasets related to the microbiology data obtained in the project and will be regularly updated during the implementation of the Project.

Summary of the Project: Osteomyelitis, a chronic, recurrent and difficult-to-treat infection, requires long-term antibacterial treatment, but poor vascularization around bone tissues hinders optimal drug delivery. The rapid development of antibacterial resistance, formation of biofilms, intracellular infections, and the need for two operations are urgent unanswered problems associated with osteomyelitis. The Project's overall goal is to develop a thermosensitive, injectable, dually loaded PLGA nanocarrier and free antibiotic-co-loaded hydrogel drug delivery system for a synergic and targeted treatment of chronic osteomyelitis. The project will attempt to reach this goal by testing the antibacterial and bone-affinity properties of commonly used antibiotics, synthesized antibiotic-bisphosphonate conjugates, phenolic acids, as well as combinations of compounds, on both reference strains and clinical isolates. Further, nanocarrier and hydrogel drug delivery systems will be synthesized and characterized in terms of physicochemical properties and antimicrobial potential.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS Izp-2025/1-0108

Grant

Researchers

Researcher, Researcher, Lead project participant, Lead project participant , Aiva Plotniece (orcid:0000-0003-2187-5693), Arkadij Sobolev (0000-0002-5517-1240), Lead project participant

Organizations

Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis (LIOS), Rīga Stradiņš University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data management plan for project "Smart injectable nanoparticle-loaded hydrogel for synergic and targeted treatment of osteomyelitis (SinGel)"

Description:

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is prepared in the framework of the Latvian Council of Science Fundamental and Applied Research project "Smart injectable nanoparticle-loaded hydrogel for synergic and targeted treatment of osteomyelitis (SinGel)" (Nr. LZP-2025/1-0108), 01.01.2026-31.12.2028. The project is implemented in the Faculty of Pharmacy at Rīga Stradiņš University and Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis. The DMP contains descriptions of datasets related to the microbiology data obtained in the project and will be regularly updated during the implementation of the Project.

Summary of the Project: Osteomyelitis, a chronic, recurrent and difficult-to-treat infection, requires long-term antibacterial treatment, but poor vascularization around bone tissues hinders optimal drug delivery. The rapid development of antibacterial resistance, formation of biofilms, intracellular infections, and the need for two operations are urgent unanswered problems associated with osteomyelitis. The Project's overall goal is to develop a thermosensitive, injectable, dually loaded PLGA nanocarrier and free antibiotic-co-loaded hydrogel drug delivery system for a synergic and targeted treatment of chronic osteomyelitis. The project will attempt to reach this goal by testing the antibacterial and bone-affinity properties of commonly used antibiotics, synthesized antibiotic-bisphosphonate conjugates, phenolic acids, as well as combinations of compounds, on both reference strains and clinical isolates. Further, nanocarrier and hydrogel drug delivery systems will be synthesized and characterized in terms of physicochemical properties and antimicrobial potential.

Researchers:

Researcher

Researcher

Lead project participant

Lead project participant

Aiva Plotniece (orcid:0000-0003-2187-5693)

Arkadij Sobolev (0000-0002-5517-1240)

Lead project participant

Organizations:

Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis (LIOS)
Rīga Stradiņš University

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: lzp-2025/1-0108

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Restricted

4. Templates

Descriptions

Dataset 1 — Antibacterial activity of antibiotics, phenolic acids, and their combinations/conjugates on osteomyelitis-inducing bacteria (reference strains)

Dataset 1 — Antibacterial activity of antibiotics (AB), phenolic acids (PA), and their combinations/conjugates on osteomyelitis-inducing bacteria (reference strains) — covers the results following antibacterial testing methods: minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)/minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC), Fractional Inhibitory Concentration Index (FICI), biofilm inhibition assay, biofilm penetration assay. The antibacterial activity is tested against *S. aureus* ATCC 25923, MRSA, *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *E. coli* ATCC 25922 strains.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Data Management Plan | Data management plan for project "Smart injectable nanoparticle-loaded hydrogel for synergic and targeted treatment of osteomyelitis (SinGel)" LICENSE:CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 14/01/2026

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This dataset covers microbiological data on the antibacterial activity of AB, PA, AB/PA combinations and synthesized conjugates against reference strains of osteomyelitis-inducing bacteria of the SinGel project.

The purpose is to determine the antibacterial activity of phenolic acids and commonly used antibiotics and determine, if the activity of antibiotics can be enhanced by using combinations of AB and PA or by synthesizing AB-PA conjugates.

The compounds are tested against reference-strains of osteomyelitis-inducing bacteria - *S. aureus* ATCC 25923, MRSA, *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 27853, *E. coli* ATCC 25922.

Antibacterial testing results include data of MIC/MBC assay, synergy test (FICI), biofilm inhibition assay and biofilm penetration assay.

These data provide the foundation for subsequent nanoparticle and hydrogel formulation and testing, directly supporting the SinGel project's SO1-SO3.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

This dataset will be valuable to researchers and students at RSU and other academic institutions working in pharmaceutical chemistry, microbiology, biomaterials and drug-delivery systems.

It can also be reused by clinical microbiology and infection-control laboratories studying antibiotic resistance or biofilm formation, as well as by governmental and non-governmental health organisations engaged in antimicrobial resistance monitoring and policy development.

Private sector companies, including pharmaceutical and biotechnology enterprises, may apply the data to develop or validate new antibacterial agents and drug delivery technologies.

Private sector companies, including pharmaceutical and biotechnology enterprises, may apply the data to develop or validate new antibacterial agents and drug delivery technologies.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- XLS
- JPG
- Others

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

The combined volume of all SinGel datasets is expected to remain within 50 GB.

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

At the time of the project proposal submission and the creation of this document, no existing datasets met the project's objectives; these data will therefore be generated within the SinGel project.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Codebook

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Files will follow a consistent naming pattern that captures project, dataset, experiment, version and date, such as: SinGel_D1_MIC_v1_30-06-2025.csv

- Project name – SinGel
- Dataset – D1
- Experiment – MIC
- Version – v1
- Date – 30-06-2025
- File format – .csv

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected file format is CSV, which at the time of preparing this document is widely used and can be opened on common software.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

CSV files can be opened and processed on numerous free platforms, including spreadsheet applications (e.g., Google Sheets, LibreOffice Calc), plain-text editors (e.g., Notepad, TextEdit, VS Code), and data-analysis environments (e.g., Python with pandas, R). Because CSV files consist of plain text with data separated by commas or other delimiters, no proprietary software is required.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

Yes

NCBI Taxonomy

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

2.2.5 Other relevant remarks

Primary and processed results will be shared in open, non-proprietary formats.

Where instrument-specific raw data are unavoidable, they will be accompanied by open-format processed files and explanatory documentation, ensuring long-term accessibility and compatibility with common software tools.

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.1 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Riga Stradins University Dataverse

RSU Dataverse is an open institutional repository that ensures licensing, long term preservation of the data. Also it uses appropriate metadata standard to describe this data.

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

Yes

2029-01-06

The embargo period will depend on the publication requirements of the scientific journals associated with the project's planned manuscripts.

Data will remain closed until the related articles are submitted and accepted, ensuring that no unpublished results are prematurely disclosed.

If additional follow-up research or funding applications based on the same datasets are in progress, the embargo may be extended accordingly, but not beyond the maximum period permitted by RSU and FAIR data policies.

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2029-01-06

The datasets will be made publicly available at the end of the embargo period.

The end date of the embargo period will be specified in the final updated version of the DMP, which may be revised within one month after the project is completed.

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

2.3.7 Other relevant remarks

Any minor updates after initial publication will be tracked through RSU Dataverse version history.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

The SinGel project budget provides dedicated personnel resources for preparing, documenting, and curating scientific research data.

All datasets – antibacterial activity tested on reference strains and clinical isolates - will be stored and maintained in full compliance with RSU and international FAIR data management standards.

The RSU Dataverse infrastructure covers the costs of secure storage, access control, archiving, and long-term preservation, so no additional institutional or external funding is required.

If minor unforeseen expenses occur, they will be covered within the project budget.

To ensure maximum data security and integrity, all scientific data will be duplicated in real time on encrypted external data carriers in parallel with RSU's secure servers:

- Primary storage – RSU servers (U: drive) with controlled, password-protected access and automatic institutional backups.
- Secondary mirrored storage – encrypted external data carriers that are regularly updated to match the server copies and kept in physically secure RSU and/ or partner facilities. These encrypted external data carriers are required because a part of the project data will be generated using specialized laboratory equipment operating on manufacturer-supplied computers that are not connected to the RSU U: drive, as well as in partner organizations where direct access to RSU servers is not always technically feasible. The external data carriers therefore serve as a secure and controlled means for transferring and temporarily mirroring data before and alongside storage on RSU servers.

This double-location, continuously updated storage strategy guarantees that:

- scientific data remain current, accurate, and retrievable at any point,
- there is an independent backup for disaster recovery, and
- long-term preservation fully meets RSU and international FAIR data management requirements.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

- Riga Stradiņš University
- Latvian Institute of Organic Synthesis (LIOS)

RSU will provide overall data management, storage in RSU Dataverse, metadata creation, long-term preservation, and access control in line with FAIR principles.

LIOS will generate and document chemical synthesis and analytical data, supply raw and processed files, and assist in preparing the dataset and metadata for repository deposit.

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and maintenance of the data management plan?

Dace Bandere (0000-0001-9144-8799)

Overall coordination of data management will rest with the SinGel project leadership at RSU, ensuring compliance with RSU regulations and FAIR data principles.

The scientific work-package leaders and key researchers will be responsible for generating, curating and verifying the primary data within their respective work packages.

All partners, including RSU and the LIOS, will contribute to quality control, preparation of metadata, and deposition of final datasets in the RSU Dataverse repository.

3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors-researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

- Researcher
- Dace Bandere (0000-0001-9144-8799)
- Ingus Skadins (0000-0003-4044-8750)
- Arkadij Sobolev (0000-0002-5517-1240)
- Karlis Pajuste (orcid: [0000-0001-8558-601X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8558-601X))
- Agnese Brangule (orcid: [0000-0003-1194-0746](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1194-0746))
- Aiva Plotniece (orcid: [0000-0003-2187-5693](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2187-5693))

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Data quality assurance processes are foreseen throughout the project implementation period and after project completion. Data collection, analysis and reporting will follow the established RSU Project Management System, which requires regular internal control procedures, including monthly documentation submission and quarterly scientific progress reporting. In addition, project progress, scientific outcomes and potential deviations will be monitored by risk-management measures outlined in the project plan, including a regularly updated risk register and corrective actions.

Experimental data will be generated using recognised and widely applied analytical, microbiological and chemical methodologies.

Microbiological testing will be performed in accordance with recognised international standards, including EUCAST and relevant ISO guidelines. Data collected by students will be subject to regular supervision and verification by experienced scientific staff to ensure accuracy and consistency. All reagents used in experimental work will comply with the required purity grades appropriate for the applied analytical, microbiological, and chemical methodologies.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control
- Other

Controlled RSU network access

During the project all digital files will be stored on RSU secure servers (e.g. U:\ drive) with the following protections:

Password-protected accounts and individual access rights, so that only authorised project staff can view or modify the files.

Firewall and RSU network protection, ensuring that the data are accessible only from RSU's internal network or through secure VPN.

RSU data storing services also ensure data encryption.

Physical access control to RSU facilities and LIOS laboratories where raw experimental data and instruments are located.

Regular back-ups performed by RSU IT services to prevent data loss.

Controlled RSU network access ("Describe these data security provisions, taking into account these shall be applied also before publishing data here") to enable adjustment of user permissions as the project progresses.

After project completion, the final, curated dataset will be deposited in the RSU Dataverse repository, which provides long-term secure storage, persistent DOI, and controlled access management in line with FAIR principles.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

During the research phase, all raw and processed data will be stored on secure RSU servers (e.g. U:\ drive) with password-protected individual access and RSU firewall protection.

Access rights will be granted only to authorised SinGel team members and can be adjusted as project roles change (data access).

Data exchange between RSU and LIOS will take place over encrypted, institutionally approved channels, ensuring that no unprotected copies remain on personal devices.

Regular automated back-ups performed by RSU IT services will safeguard against accidental loss and ensure data recovery.

Controlled internal data sharing will take place only among approved project participants until the dataset is deposited in the RSU Dataverse repository for open access after publication.

These measures guarantee the integrity and confidentiality of raw and processed data throughout the project and before formal publishing.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

During the active research phase reference-strain experimental data will be stored on secure RSU servers (U: drive) with restricted, password-protected access for authorised SinGel team members.

Primary experimental files generated at the LIOS (raw data) will be stored on LIOS's secure institutional servers with equivalent access controls and regular backups.

Data exchange between RSU and LIOS will occur over encrypted, institutionally approved channels, ensuring that no unprotected copies remain on personal devices. If direct secure network transfer is not technically feasible, encrypted external data carriers may be used as an interim solution for data transfer between RSU and LIOS; the specific procedures will be finalised in coordination with LIOS.

These provisions apply from the moment raw data are generated and remain in force until the final dataset is deposited in RSU Dataverse for long-term preservation and public access.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

As the project generates non-sensitive scientific data, formal controlled destruction procedures are not required. Following publication in the RSU

Dataverse repository, temporary working copies held on local devices (e.g., institutional computers or drives) will be removed using standard electronic file deletion. Physical laboratory materials will be discarded in accordance with RSU internal laboratory and safety regulations upon completion of analyses. As no personal data are collected, specialist destruction documentation or verification processes are not necessary.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

No

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

No

Dataset 2 — Antibacterial activity of antibiotics, phenolic acids, and their combinations/conjugates on osteomyelitis-inducing bacteria (clinical isolates)

Dataset 2 — Antibacterial activity of antibiotics (AB), phenolic acids (PA), and their combinations/conjugates on osteomyelitis-inducing bacteria (clinical isolates) — covers the results following antibacterial testing methods: minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC)/minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC), Fractional Inhibitory Concentration Index (FICI), biofilm inhibition assay, biofilm penetration assay. Clinical bacterial isolates – the biological starting material – will be obtained from osteomyelitis operations at the Hospital of Traumatology and Orthopedics (TOS).

An institutional ethics approval will be secured, with the milestone approval obtained by month 6 (Mo6) of the project.

These isolates are essential for the SinGel project, which aims to enhance the antibacterial and/or bone-affinity properties of ABs.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

This dataset covers microbiological data on the antibacterial activity of AB, PA, AB/PA combinations and synthesized conjugates against clinical isolates of the SinGel project. Clinical isolates will serve as clinically relevant test organisms, providing larger translational potential of the obtained results.

The origin of the data is the TOS, where bacterial strains will be collected from osteomyelitis surgical operations.

Collection will take place only after an institutional ethics approval has been obtained (milestone: month 6).

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

This dataset will serve researchers and students in microbiology, infectious diseases, orthopaedics, and biomaterials at RSU and other universities.

It will also be useful to clinical laboratories and infection-control services that require authentic osteomyelitis-related bacterial strains, and to governmental or non-governmental organisations monitoring antimicrobial resistance.

Industrial partners in the pharmaceutical and biotech sectors can build on these clinically relevant isolates for the development of novel antibacterial therapies and diagnostic tools.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Clinical data
- Experimental data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- XLS
- JPG
- Others

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

The combined volume of all three SinGel datasets is expected to remain within 50 GB.

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

These clinical bacterial isolates will be collected specifically for the SinGel project; there are no existing datasets available that meet the project's objectives.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Codebook

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

Files will follow a consistent naming pattern that captures project, dataset, experiment, version and date, such as:

SinGel_D2_MIC_v1_30-06-2025.csv

- Project name – SinGel
- Dataset – D2
- Experiment – MIC
- Version – v1
- Date – 30-06-2025
- File format – .csv

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected file format is CSV, which at the time of preparing this document is widely used and can be opened on common software.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

CSV files can be opened and processed on numerous free platforms, including spreadsheet applications (e.g., Google Sheets, LibreOffice Calc), plain-text editors (e.g., Notepad, TextEdit, VS Code), and data-analysis environments (e.g., Python with pandas, R). Because CSV files consist of plain text with data separated by commas or other delimiters, no proprietary software is required.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Cite Taxonom

2.2.5 Other relevant remarks

Primary and processed results will be shared in open, non-proprietary formats.

Where instrument-specific raw data are unavoidable, they will be accompanied by open-format processed files and explanatory documentation, ensuring long-term accessibility and compatibility with common software tools.

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.1 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Riga Stradins University dataverse

RSU Dataverse is an open institutional repository that ensures licensing, long term preservation of the data. Also it uses appropriate metadata standart to describe this data.

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

Yes

2029-01-06

The embargo period will depend on the publication requirements of the scientific journals associated with the project's planned manuscripts.

Data will remain closed until the related articles are submitted and accepted, ensuring that no unpublished results are prematurely disclosed.

If additional follow-up research or funding applications based on the same datasets are in progress, the embargo may be extended accordingly, but not beyond the maximum period permitted by RSU and FAIR data policies.

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2029-01-06

If possible, indicate approximate date for that

The datasets will be made publicly available at the end of the embargo period.

The end date of the embargo period will be specified in the final updated version of the DMP, which may be revised within one month after the project is completed.

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

2.3.7 Other relevant remarks

The dataset will include clear statements on ethical approval and de-identification procedures, so that secondary users can confidently reuse the data in compliance with clinical research standards.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

The SinGel project budget includes dedicated personnel resources for preparing, documenting, and curating scientific research data generated from clinical bacterial isolates collected during osteomyelitis operations at the TOS.

All data will be stored and maintained in full compliance with RSU and international FAIR data management standards.

The RSU Dataverse infrastructure will cover all costs related to secure storage, access control, archiving, and long-term preservation, so no extra institutional or external funding is required.

If minor unforeseen costs arise they will be covered within the project budget.

To guarantee data security and integrity, all clinical and microbiological data will be duplicated in real time on encrypted external data carriers in parallel with RSU's secure servers:

Primary storage – RSU servers (U: drive) and secure TOS servers with password-protected access and automatic institutional backups.

Secondary mirrored storage – encrypted external data carriers that are regularly updated to match the server copies and kept in secure RSU and partner facilities. These encrypted external data carriers are required because a part of the project data will be generated using specialized laboratory equipment operating on manufacturer-supplied computers that are not connected to the RSU U: drive, as well as in partner organizations where direct access to RSU servers is not always technically feasible. The external data carriers therefore serve as a secure and controlled means for transferring and temporarily mirroring data before and alongside storage on RSU servers.

This double-location, continuously updated storage strategy ensures that the clinical isolate datasets remain current, accurate, and retrievable, and that long-

term preservation fully meets RSU and international FAIR data management requirements.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

- Riga Stradiņš University
- TOS

TOS will collect and document the clinical material from osteomyelitis operations according to the ethics protocol. The material will be handed over to RSU for further microbiological testing.

RSU will oversee data management, including secure storage, metadata creation, preparation of the final dataset, and deposition in the RSU Dataverse repository.

Collaboration ensures that collection, processing, and long-term preservation comply with ethical approvals and FAIR data principles.

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and maintenance of the data management plan?

Dace Bandere (0000-0001-9144-8799)

Overall coordination of data management will rest with the SinGel project leadership at RSU, ensuring compliance with RSU regulations, the approved ethics protocol, and FAIR data principles.

The clinical partner at TOS will be responsible for the secure collection, initial documentation, and transfer of bacterial isolates and related metadata under the approved ethics agreement.

The RSU research team will manage subsequent curation, long-term storage, and deposition of the final dataset in the RSU Dataverse repository.

3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors-researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

- Researcher
- Dace Bandere (0000-0001-9144-8799)
- Ingus Skadins (0000-0003-4044-8750)
- Agnese Brangule (orcid: [0000-0003-1194-0746](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1194-0746))
- Aiva Plotniece (orcid: [0000-0003-2187-5693](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2187-5693))
- Arkadij Sobolev (0000-0002-5517-1240)
- Karlis Pajuste (orcid: [0000-0001-8558-601X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8558-601X))

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Data quality assurance processes are foreseen throughout the project implementation period and after project completion. Data collection, analysis and reporting will follow the established RSU Project Management System, which requires regular internal control procedures, including monthly documentation submission and quarterly scientific progress reporting. In addition, project progress, scientific outcomes and potential deviations will be monitored by risk-management measures outlined in the project plan, including a regularly updated risk register and corrective actions.

Experimental data will be generated using recognised and widely applied analytical, microbiological and chemical methodologies.

Microbiological testing will be performed in accordance with recognised international standards, including EUCAST and relevant ISO guidelines. Data collected by students will be subject to regular supervision and verification by experienced scientific staff to ensure accuracy and consistency. All reagents used in experimental work will comply with the required purity grades appropriate for the applied analytical, microbiological, and chemical methodologies.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control
- Other

Controlled RSU network access

During the project all digital files will be stored on RSU secure servers (e.g. U:\ drive) with the following protections:

Password-protected accounts and individual access rights, so that only authorised project staff can view or modify the files.

Firewall and RSU network protection, ensuring that the data are accessible only from RSU's internal network or through secure VPN.

RSU IT infrastructure also ensures data encryption.

Physical access control to RSU facilities and LIOS laboratories where raw experimental data and instruments are located.

Regular back-ups performed by RSU IT services to prevent data loss.

Controlled RSU network access ("Other") to enable adjustment of user permissions as the project progresses.

After project completion, the final, curated dataset will be deposited in the RSU Dataverse repository, which provides long-term secure storage, persistent DOI, and controlled access management in line with FAIR principles.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission

- Data recovery
- Data sharing

During the project, clinical bacterial isolates will be obtained at TOS under the hospital's internal clinical and data governance procedures. The biological sample obtained is a bacterial sample from infectious site for inoculation of bacteria. No patient-identifiable information will be transferred outside TOS. No patient tissue samples will be obtained. RSU will receive only biological samples without any personal or coded patient data, together with minimal non-identifying contextual information necessary for laboratory analyses. Ethical approval for the collection and research use of these samples has been issued by TOS (Ethics approval No. 43/2025, approved on 11.12.2025), and includes the informed consent documentation.

All digital research files generated at RSU will be stored on secure university servers (e.g. U:\ drive) with password-protected accounts and individual access rights to ensure that only authorised project staff may view or modify data. Access will be further protected through firewall and RSU network security measures, enabling entry only via the internal RSU network or through secure VPN connection.

Physical access to RSU laboratories and LIOS facilities where raw experimental data and instruments are located will be restricted to authorised personnel. Regular automated back-ups managed by RSU IT services will ensure data integrity and recoverability, and user access rights will be adjusted as project roles evolve.

Data transfer between TOS and RSU will occur only through secure, institutionally approved procedures, ensuring that research materials and data remain protected prior to publication.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

During the active research phase, clinical isolate data will be stored on secure RSU servers (U: drive) with restricted, password-protected access for authorised SinGel team members.

Primary sample data obtained at the TOS will be stored on TOS will be stored on TOS servers under the hospital's secure access controls and routine back-up procedures. Once anonymised sample identifiers and laboratory data are transferred to RSU, they will be incorporated into the RSU data structure and protected under the same security measures as all other project files.

Data exchange between TOS and RSU will take place over encrypted, institutionally approved channels, ensuring that no unprotected copies remain on personal devices or transmitted via unsecured platforms.

These provisions apply from the moment raw data are generated and remain in force until the final dataset is deposited in RSU Dataverse for long-term preservation and public access.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

As the project generates non-sensitive scientific data, formal controlled destruction procedures are not required. Following publication in the RSU Dataverse repository, temporary working copies held on local devices (e.g., institutional computers or drives) will be removed using standard electronic file deletion. Physical laboratory materials will be discarded in accordance with RSU internal laboratory and safety regulations upon completion of analyses. As no personal data are collected, specialist destruction documentation or verification processes are not necessary.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The project participants will not receive any personal data related to the clinical isolates; RSU will receive only anonymised isolate codes together with the clinical

indication of osteomyelitis. The biological sample obtained is a bacterial sample from infectious site for inoculation of bacteria. No patient tissue samples will be obtained.

All clinical bacterial isolates will be anonymised at source at TOS before inclusion in the research dataset, ensuring that no identifiers (e.g., name or personal ID number) are transferred outside the hospital. No additional demographic or clinical information (such as age, sex, comorbidities, medication history or surgery date) will be provided to the project.

Clinical materials and patient-identifying information will be handled exclusively at TOS under the hospital's internal clinical and data governance procedures. RSU and LIOS will receive only coded isolates and related laboratory results, and cannot re-identify the individuals from whom the isolates originate. Although the dataset contains health information (osteomyelitis diagnosis), the coding system ensures that the isolates are functionally anonymised for RSU and LIOS research purposes.

All links between isolate codes and patient identity will remain within TOS and will not be shared with RSU or LIOS. Access to coded samples and related electronic records at RSU will be restricted to authorised project staff under secure data-management procedures.

No direct patient contact or project-specific recruitment will take place. TOS will obtain and manage patient informed consent within its standard clinical workflow, and only anonymised isolates and the required clinical indication will be transferred to the research team.

This process is covered by TOS ethical approval No. 43/2025 (11.12.2025).

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

No

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

- Anonymising data
- Privacy policies
- National laws

All clinical bacterial isolates will be fully anonymized before inclusion in the research dataset. Any links between isolates and patient-identifying data will remain only within the TOS and will not be transferred to RSU. Access to raw materials and related records will be limited to authorised project staff under strict privacy constraints and in full compliance with national data protection laws and the approved institutional ethics protocol. The published dataset will contain only non-identifiable strain-level data and experimental results, ensuring there is no possibility of patient re-identification.

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